

Kinetics of Osmium(VIII)-catalysed Oxidation of Methyl Phenyl Sulphide by Bromamine-B

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Kinetics of osmium(VIII)-catalysed oxidation of methyl phenyl sulphide by bromamine-B (BAB) in alkaline medium have been followed in *t*-butanol-water (1 : 1, v/v). The reaction product was methyl phenyl sulphoxide. The rate law has been derived. Thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated. A suitable mechanism has also been proposed.

AROMATIC sulphonyl haloamines act as halonium cations, hypohalites and N-anions which act as bases and nucleophiles. Recently, sodium *N*-bromobenzene sulphonamide¹ (bromamine-B, BAB) was found to be a useful redox analytical reagent in acidic and alkaline media. We report here the kinetics of oxidation of methyl phenyl sulphide by BAB in alkaline medium, catalysed by OsO₄.

Experimental

Methyl phenyl sulphide and bromamine-B were prepared by reported methods¹. Standard solution of OsO₄ (Johnson and Matthey) was prepared in NaOH solution. First order rate constants were determined under pseudo-first order kinetic conditions. The reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted BAB iodometrically.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry (1 : 1) of the oxidation was determined with varying amounts of oxidant in large excess of the substrate. The product methyl phenyl sulphoxide was obtained (identified by coltic) after carrying out the reaction for 48 h, and formed accordingly,

The order with respect to [BAB] is found to be one as evidenced by the linear plot of log titre vs time. The rate of reaction is found to be an inverse function of [BAB] (Table 1), suggesting that this [BAB] may be in equilibrium with a less reactive species, i.e. a dimer or *N,N*-dibromobenzenesulphonamide,

The idea that *N*-halocompounds like chloramine-T² and bromamine-T³ existing in equilibrium with the corresponding *N,N*-dihalocompounds is well known.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF REACTANTS ON REACTION RATE AT 30° IN ALKALINE MEDIUM

[OH⁻] = 1 × 10⁻³ M, [OsO₄] = 1.2715 × 10⁻⁴ M, *t*-Butanol = 50%

[BAB] × 10 ³ M	[MPS] × 10 ² M	<i>k</i> ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
1.12	3.06	2.80
1.68	3.06	2.46
2.24	3.06	2.32
2.81	3.06	2.20
1.66	1.98	1.79
1.66	2.97	2.63
1.66	3.95	3.20
1.66	4.95	3.81
2.0 ^a	3.02	2.51
2.0 ^b	3.02	2.55
2.0 ^c	3.02	2.57

^a[OH⁻] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, ^b[OH⁻] = 1.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, ^c[OH⁻] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³.

The rate increases steadily with increase in [sulphide] and a plot of log *k*₁ vs log [sulphide] is linear (*r* = 0.997) with a slope less than unity (0.81), indicating a fractional order dependence of rate on [sulphide] (Table 1). Varying either [OH⁻] or the ionic strength has no effect on the reaction rate (Table 1). The rate increases with increase in [OsO₄] (Table 2). Thus a plot of log *k*₁ vs log [OsO₄] is linear (*r* = 0.996) with a slope 0.79 (Fig. 1A).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF CATALYST AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANT ON RATE OF OXIDATION

[BAB] = 2.01 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [MPS] = 3.02 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 303 K

<i>t</i> -Butanol %	<i>k</i> ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	[OsO ₄] × 10 ³ M	<i>k</i> ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
35	9.08	2.54	0.67
45	3.43	5.09	1.06
50	2.30	7.63	1.49
65	0.79	10.17	1.97
		12.71	2.41

The rate data at different compositions of *t*-butanol (Table 2) show that the rate increases with the polarity of the medium, indicating a

possible formation of charge activated complex in the transition state which is more hydrated than the reactants. The reaction was carried out at three different temperatures 30, 35 and 40°. The values are $E_a = 16.4 \pm 3.2$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta H^\ddagger = 13.87 \pm 1.0$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -245.5 \pm 34.7$ J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ and $\Delta G^\ddagger$ (at 303 K) = 88.27 ± 4.2 kJ mol⁻¹. The possibility of radical involvement in the reaction is ruled out as the addition of acrylonitrile in the reaction mixture developed no turbidity.

Mechanism: With the use of BAB, the possible oxidising species are BAB, RNHBr, HOBr, BrO⁻ and RNBBr₂. In a strong or moderate alkaline medium, the possibility of either RNBBr₂ or HOBr being the oxidising species is rare^{4,5}. If RNHBr is the reactive species, the increase in alkalinity of the medium will decrease the reaction rate. But increase of [OH⁻] has no effect on the rate. Again BrO⁻ predominates only in strong alkaline medium. Hence under the present experimental conditions BAB is the probable oxidising species.

Octahedral complexes of the form *trans* [OsO₄(OH)₂]²⁻ and [OsO₄(OH)(H₂O)]⁻ have been reported by Griffith⁶. In alkaline medium Os^{VIII} possibly exists⁷ in the form of reactive species [OsO₄(OH)₂]²⁻. For brevity the foregoing formulation is indicated as OsO₄^{*} in the reaction scheme.

On the basis of the foregoing kinetic data, a polar mechanism may be proposed for the oxidation of sulphide by BAB. A cyclic complex between BAB and OsO₄ would explain well the observed facts, perhaps supported by the large negative entropy of the reaction. A similar situation was explained by Mushran and coworkers on the oxidation of α-hydroxyacids⁸ and ketones⁹ by alkaline CAT catalysed by OsO₄.

Applying steady state treatment after omitting the higher term, the rate law can be written as

$$\frac{-d[\text{BAB}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{BAB}][\text{S}][\text{OsO}_4]_0}{1 + K_1[\text{S}] + K_1[\text{OsO}_4]_0} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where, } k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{S}][\text{OsO}_4]_0}{1 + K_1[\text{S}] + K_1[\text{OsO}_4]_0} \quad (2)$$

The rate law accords well with the observed kinetic orders in sulphide, oxidant, OH⁻ and OsO₄. Under the condition [OsO₄] << [S], equation (2) will be

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{S}][\text{OsO}_4]_0}{1 + K_1[\text{S}]}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} &= \frac{1}{k_2 K_1 [\text{S}][\text{OsO}_4]_0} + \frac{1}{k_2 [\text{OsO}_4]_0} \\ \frac{[\text{OsO}_4]_0}{k_{\text{obs}}} &= \frac{1}{[\text{S}]} \frac{1}{K_1 k_2} + \frac{1}{k_2} \end{aligned}$$

Thus the plot of [OsO₄]₀/k_{obs} vs 1/[S] is linear (Fig. 1B) with a positive intercept on Y-axis, supports the above mechanism.

Fig. 1. (A) Plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{OsO}_4]$; [BAB] = 2.01×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [MPS] = 3.02×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³. (B) Plot of $[\text{OsO}_4]_0/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$; [BAB] = 1.66×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [OsO₄] = 1.27×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³.

A detailed mechanism of oxidation is shown in the following Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The fact that the order is less than one in sulphide is consistent with the assumption that equilibrium involving the complex formation of sulphide and OsO₄ preceded the rate-limiting step. The formation of complex prior to rate-limiting step is also indicated by a plot of 1/k_{obs} vs 1/[S] ($r = 0.998$) with a positive intercept.

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